

Deep soil disturbance influenced soil organic matter concentration of agricultural lands of Turbat, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

*Agricultural management practices influence soil properties. Conservation agriculture with diversified cropping system promotes soil quality over conservation agriculture under monocropping system. In this study, three orchards, three croplands and three tree-based intercropping systems (TBI) in Turbat, Balochistan, Pakistan were sampled for the assessment of soil quality. The soil samples were collected from 0-10 cm depth from five random sites within each selected field site. The mesofauna (128 mm to <2mm in size) and macrofauna (≥ 2 mm body size) found in the soil samples and on the soil surface, under the range of eye sight from the place of soil sample collection, were also collected in plastic bottles containing 5% formaline solution. The results show that orchards and TBI systems were more than 200 years old fields; whereas, croplands were 30-35 years old. The orchard fields, were under manual deep tillage practices; whereas, the land cultivated with crops in between trees in TBI systems and the croplands were under shallow tillage practices. The orchard fields had significantly lower soil organic matter (SOM) contents (7.67 to 9.09 g kg⁻¹) than croplands (13.17 to 16.14 g kg⁻¹) and TBI system fields (12.72 to 14.99 g kg⁻¹; $P < 0.05$). No significant differences in the SOM contents were observed between TBI fields and croplands. These TBI systems and croplands were under shallow tillage practices. Despite of significantly low contents of SOM, orchard fields had the same number of species of soil fauna as other fields. Total 12 soil mesofauna and soil macrofauna were identified. The two ant species; red-headed large-sized ant (*Solenopsis invicta*) and small black ant (*Camponotus pennsylvanica*) were found in all fields. Our results demonstrate that long-term deep tillage had adverse effect on the SOM contents.*

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Introduction

Food demand is increasing day by day due to increasing population. World agriculture and land available for agriculture is getting limited with time due to increasing rate of urbanization and industrialization. The agricultural systems of the world are divided into two main types; conventional agriculture and conservation agriculture. The conventional agriculture involves the use of deep tillage (soil disturbance \geq 30 cm depth), monocropping system, the use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides (Farooq and Siddiqui, 2015). The conventional farming is an old system; the tillage of agricultural soil has history of thousands of years (Farooq and Siddiqui, 2015). The use of heavy vehicles for tillage purpose stated in the middle of 20th century; similarly, the use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides in this system gain momentum at the same time (Pimentel, 1996; Farooq and Siddiqui, 2015). Moreover, this system is the major agricultural system all over the world (Farooq and Siddiqui, 2015; Durham and Mizik, 2023). In contrast, conservation agricultural system idea emerged from the “Dust Bowls” catastrophe that happened in 1930, in the midwestern region of the United States of America and was proposed by Edward H. Faulkner (1945). This system involves minimum tillage (shallow tillage and less frequent), less use of synthetic fertilizer and pesticides, the use of organic fertilizers such as crop residue return after the harvest of crop, mulching on soil surface, compost and manure application in soil, crop diversification with cover cropping, crop rotation and tree-based intercropping (Durham and Mizik, 2023; Francaviglia et al., 2023; Reicosky et al., 2023).

The agricultural management systems have a significant and profound influence on soil quality. Conventional agriculture reduces soil organic matter (SOM) because the tillage of soil breaks soil aggregates and exposes organic matter for decomposition (Reicosky et al., 2023; Francaviglia et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2025; Xiao et al., 2025). The loss of SOM also reduces the binding of soil clay particles with other mineral particles as aggregates thus causes soil erosion (Xiao et al., 2025). The Dust Bowl catastrophe is an example of soil erosion due to conventional agriculture (Reicosky et al., 2023). Conventional agriculture also reduces the abundances of soil fauna especially earthworms (Domínguez et al., 2024; Rodríguez et al., 2025). Soil fauna play very important role in soil fertility (Coleman et al., 2024). In contrast to conventional agriculture, conservation agriculture increases SOM content significantly (Reicosky et al., 2023), reduces soil erosion (Roman-Vazquez et al., 2025), increases the abundances of soil meso and macrofauna (Coleman et al., 2024; Rodríguez et al., 2025) increases soil nutrients (Wen et al., 2025; Zhu et al., 2025) and improves crop production (Zhu

et al., 2025). Turbat, is a warm desert located in Balochistan, Pakistan; where the average daytime temperature is 45°C from May to July and less than 250 mm rainfall occurs per year. The source of income of people, is farming and livestock. Less occurrence of rainfall and high temperature are the major obstacles in the sector of agriculture in this region. Date palm is the major crop in Turbat. Cotton, rice, Medicago, lemon, okra (ladyfinger) are also grown in this region. No research till date has been conducted to evaluate the soil properties under various agricultural management systems in this region. This kind of knowledge can help farmers and policy makers to adapt the best system or management practice for soil quality improvement of agricultural lands of Turbat. This study aims to 1) survey three orchards, three croplands and three tree-based intercropping (TBI) systems and ask farmers for agricultural management systems of these agricultural lands, 2) the soil samples were collected from those selected fields for quality assessment and 3) soil meso fauna and macrofauna abundances of those selected fields were assessed.

Material and Methods

Study site, selection of farming fields and collection of information from local farmers

This research study was performed in the agriculture fields of Turbat, Balochistan, Pakistan (26°03' N, 63°05' E). The weather of Turbat is warm and dry and the cumulative annual rainfall is less than 250 mm. The average maximum (daytime) temperature from May to July is ~45°C (Table 1).

Table 1. Rainfall, average minimum and average maximum temperature of Turbat, Balochistan, Pakistan during January 01, 2024 till December 31, 2024

Month	Rainfall (mm)	Minimum temperature (°C)	Maximum temperature (°C)
January	4	14.93	25.29
February	13.3	16.13	25.93
March	9.6	17.45	29.00
April	39.9	22.40	33.26
May	2	27.74	42.12
June	0	29.45	42.33
July	0	29.41	41.77
August	2.8	28.00	36.70
September	1.6	26.23	37.83
October	0	25.09	37.35
November	0	20.76	33.13
December	0	12.29	24.80

In this study 3 croplands, 3 orchards fields and 3 tree-based intercropping (TBI) fields were surveyed. High resolution pictures of each field were taken. Local community (farmers) were asked about agricultural practices, which involved 1) age of fields, 2) cropping system, 3) fertilizers applied and 4) tillage.

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Figure 1. Study field sites.

Soil sampling

From each selected field, using random walk method, soil samples were collected from five sites. In each field, soil samples were collected using compas and random number table. The first sampling was collected following the forcefully throwing a red ribben-tied stone from behind the front. The directions; east, west, north and south were numbered as 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. From the point of first sampling, the second sampling was collected using random number table and compas and 50 foot steps per sample collection. Soil samples were collected from 0-10 cm depth

using 5 cm diameter and 10 cm height. Soil samples were collected in plastic ziplock bags and were labeled.

Soil samples processing and chemical Analysis

Soil samples were brought to the Soil Testing Laboratory, Department of Botany, University of Balochistan, Quetta. The soil samples were kept open to air-dry for one week. Afterwards, samples were passed through the sieve of mesh size 2 mm. Air-dried soil samples were analyzed for pH and electrical conductivity (EC). The SOM was estimated with the help of chromic acid oxidation of Walkley-Black method. The fractions of sand, silt and clay were also assessed. All analyses were performed according to the procedures described in Estefan et al, (2013).

Soil fauna collection and identification:

During soil sample collection, soil mesofauna and macrofauna were also collected. After collection of soil, the soil was spread over a plastic sheet and the soil fauna that were found in the soil were collected in a plastic bottle (25 ml) with large screw-cap (2 cm diameter). Any soil fauna that were in the range of sight from the point of soil collection spot were also collected. The ants were not collected because they were in high abundance and only pictures were taken. The fauna were identified in the Department of Zoology, University of Balochistan.

Statistical Analysis

The differences between treatments were assessed with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and least significance difference test (LSD). All data analyses were performed on Microsoft Excel and CoSTATC softwares.

Results

The orchards and TBI-systems were the oldest with age ranging from ~200 - 350. The croplands were 30-35 years of age. All fields were receiving both synthetic and organic fertilizers. The orchard fields were under deep tillage with hands (manual). The deep tillage involved uprooting of old trees for their replacement with saplings. The orchards were cultivated with mango as a monocrop (Orchard-F1), mango, ziziphus and date palm as mix vegetation (Orchard-F2) and mango, lemon and date palm as mix vegetation (Orchard-F3). The croplands were cultivated with wheat-cotton rotation. The TBI systems were cultivated with date palm and rice (TBI-F1), date palm and medicago (TBI-F2) and date palm with pumpkin (TBI-F3).

Table 2. History of agricultural fields selected for this study

Field site	Age (yrs)	Tillage	Cropping system	Fertilizer management
Orchard F1	Approximately 250	Manual deep tillage related to uprooting of old plants for plantation of sapling	Mango trees as monocrop	Inorganic fertilizer, FYM manure, removal of residue from pruning or uprooting of old tree
Orchard F2	Approximately 250	Manual tillage related to uprooting of old plants for plantation of sapling	Mango, ziziphus and date palm as mix vegetation	Inorganic fertilizer, FYM manure, removal of residue from pruning or uprooting of old tree
Orchard F3	Approximately 250	Manual tillage related to uprooting of old plants for plantation of sapling	Mango, lemon and date palm as mix vegetation	Inorganic fertilizer, FYM manure, removal of residue from pruning or uprooting of old tree
Cropland F1	Approximately 30	Reduced (shallow) tillage with spade or shovel	Wheat – cotton rotation	Inorganic fertilizer plus approximately 50% of residue return after crop harvest
Cropland F3	Approximately 35	Reduced (shallow) tillage with spade or shovel	Wheat – cotton rotation	Inorganic fertilizer plus approximately 50% of residue return after crop harvest
Cropland F9	Approximately 35	Reduced (shallow) tillage with spade or shovel	Wheat – cotton rotation	Inorganic fertilizer plus approximately 50% of residue return after crop harvest
TBI F3	Approximately 350	Manual deep tillage related to uprooting of old plants for plantation of sapling. Shallow tillage for land under crop cultivation	Date palm and rice	Inorganic fertilizers, FYM manure, removal of residue from pruning or uprooting of old tree plus approximately 50% of residue return after crop harvest
TBI F5	Approximately 350	Manual deep tillage related to uprooting of old plants for plantation of sapling. Shallow tillage for land under crop cultivation	Date palm and medicago	Inorganic fertilizers, FYM manure, removal of residue from pruning or uprooting of old tree plus approximately 50% of residue return after crop harvest
TBI F7	Approximately 200	Manual deep tillage related to uprooting of old plants for plantation of sapling. Shallow tillage for land under crop cultivation	Date palm and pumpkin	Inorganic fertilizers, FYM manure, removal of residue from pruning or uprooting of old tree plus approximately 50% of residue return after crop harvest

The FYM manures applied in these selected agricultural farms were from cow and buffalo farms and goat and sheep farms. The inorganic fertilizers used in these selected agricultural fields were urea and Nitrophos.

The SOM contents of orchards were in the range of 7.67 to 9.09 (Figure 2). The SOM contents of croplands were in the range of 12.72 to 14.99. The SOM contents of TBI systems were in the range of 13.17 to 16.14. The orchard fields had significantly lower SOM contents than croplands and TBI system fields (Figure 2). The pH of soil of orchard fields was in the range of 8.1 to 8.8. The pH of soil of cropland fields was in the range of 8.14 to 8.39. The pH of soil of TBI system fields was in the range of 8.36 to 9 (Figure 2). The EC of soil was in the order of orchard fields < cropland fields < TBI system fields (Figure 2). The EC of orchard fields was in the range of 1.01 - 1.26 dS m⁻¹, the EC of croplands was in the range of 2.89 - 3.57 dS m⁻¹ and the EC of TBI system was in the range of 1.04 - 5.9 dS m⁻¹ (Figure 2). The texture of soil of these fields was sandy to sandy loam (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Soil organic matter (SOM; n = 5), clay, sand and silt concentrations (n = 1; pool of five replicate samples from each study site), pH and electrical conductivity (n = 1; pool of five replicate samples from each study site) of soil samples collected from study field sites. The bars of SOM data with different letters indicate significant differences (P<0.05).

Total twelve soil meso and macrofauna were found in these fields (Figure 4). These were; *Solenopsis invicta*, *Camponotus pennsylvanicus*, *Chrotogonus homalodemus*, *Leptysmia marginicollis*, German cockroach (*Blattella vaga*), unidentified insect, *Amblytropidia mysteca*, *Melanoplus decorates*, *Orphulella pelidna*, *Acentria ephemerella*, *Chrotogonus arenicola*, *Acrida exaltata*. The two-ant species red-headed large-sized ant (*Solenopsis invicta*) and Small black ant (*Camponotus pennsylvanicus*) were found in all fields. Despite of significantly low SOM contents, the number of soil fauna and number of soil fauna species was comparable to other fields (Table 1)

Figure 3. Soil fauna collected from study field sites.

Table 3. Number of soil macrofauna species, species types and number of individuals of each species from a given agroecosystem Orchards sampled of Turbat, Balochistan, Pakistan

Sampling site	Number of soil fauna species	Types of soil fauna	Number of individuals
OF1	6	Red-headed large-sized ant (<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>)	Numerous
		Small black ant (<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>)	Numerous
		Grasshopper (<i>Chrotogonus homalodemus</i>)	5
		Grasshopper (<i>Leptysmia marginicollis</i>)	1
		German cockroach	1
		Unknown insects (badly damaged, could not identified)	2
OF2	3	Red-headed large-sized ant (<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>)	Numerous
		Small black ant (<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>)	Numerous
		Grasshopper (<i>Chrotogonus homalodemus</i>)	5
OF3	5	Red-headed large-sized ant (<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>)	Numerous
		Small black ant (<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>)	Numerous
		Grasshopper (<i>Chrotogonus homalodemus</i>)	1
		Grasshopper (<i>Amblytropidia mysteca</i>)	1
		Grasshopper (<i>Melanoplus decorates</i>)	1
CF1	3	Red-headed large-sized ant (<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>)	Numerous
		Small black ant (<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>)	Numerous
		Grasshopper (<i>Chrotogonus homalodemus</i>)	2
CF2	6	Red-headed large-sized ant (<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>)	Numerous
		Small black ant (<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>)	Numerous
		Grasshopper (<i>Amblytropidia mysteca</i>)	1
		Grasshopper (<i>Orphulella pelidna</i>)	1
		Grasshopper (<i>Acrida cinerea</i>)	1
Un-identified dragonfly type insect	1		
CF3	5	Red-headed large-sized ant (<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>)	Numerous
		Small black ant (<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>)	Numerous
		Grasshopper (<i>Chrotogonus homalodemus</i>)	1
		Grasshopper (<i>Orphulella pelidna</i>)	1
TBIF1	3	Red-headed large-sized ant (<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>)	Numerous
		Small black ant (<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>)	Numerous
		Grasshopper (<i>Chrotogonus homalodemus</i>)	4
TBIF2	5	Red-headed large-sized ant (<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>)	Numerous
		Small black ant (<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>)	Numerous
		Grasshopper (<i>Chrotogonus arenicola</i>)	2
		Grasshopper (<i>Melanoplus decorates</i>)	1
		Grasshopper (<i>Leptysmia marginicollis</i>)	1
			1
TBIF3	5	Red-headed large-sized ant (<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>)	Numerous
		Small black ant (<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>)	Numerous
		Grasshopper (<i>Acrida exaltata</i>)	2
		Grasshopper (<i>Orphulella pelidna</i>)	1
		Grasshopper (<i>Amblytropidia mysteca</i>)	1

Discussion

For this research, three orchards, three croplands and three tree-based intercropping fields were taken into consideration. The orchards were approximately 250 years old under the same management practices. Mango, ziziphus, datepalm and lemon were cultivated in those orchard fields. Farmers of this region uproot the old trees and replace them with saplings. This uprooting of trees causes soil disturbance to greater depths. This acts as a deep tillage, which may be the sole reason for low SOM contents. In these fields, farmers apply synthetic fertilizers (commonly urea and nitrophos) and manure from cow and buffalo farms. Moreover, two ant species; red-headed large-sized ant (*Solenopsis invicta*) and small black ant (*Camponotus pennsylvanicus*) were found in all orchard fields. Ants play a significant major role in distributing organic matter in soil, turn the nutrients in organic matter into more plant available forms, make channels in soil

profile, which helps keep it aerated for plant roots to respire feasibly, promote soil aggregation and microbial growth and their activities in soil (Farji-Brener et al., 2017; Bonfanti et al., 2025; Muklada et al., 2025; Thanuja et al., 2025). Therefore, ants play an important role in soil fertility by improving soil physico-chemical and biological properties (Shukla et al., 2016; Casimiro et al., 2019; Anjos et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2025). The presence of ants in all study fields and in particular in orchards may explain why these fields are still cultivable.

Croplands in this region were new compared to orchards and TBI systems. These fields were under shallow tillage (shallow tillage with spade) practice and 50% of the crop residues were returned after the harvest of crops. These two factors and the use of synthetic fertilizer (urea and nitrophos) may explain why the SOM contents were significantly higher in these lands than orchards. The straw return after crop harvest increases soil organic contents more when this organic amendment is combined with synthetic fertilizer compared to residue return without synthetic fertilizer applied (Lou et al., 2011; Ninkuu et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2025). Despite of saline soil ($2.89 - 3.57 \text{ dS m}^{-1}$) in these fields, high SOM contents show that this salinity level does not affect soil microbial processes and crop production in this region.

The soil in tree-based intercropping (TBI) system fields was comparable to the SOM in croplands and was significantly higher than the SOM in orchard soil. The TBI system fields were also very old (300 to 350 years of age). The fields under tree cultivation were also under deep tillage because of uprooting of old trees but the soil under crop cultivation (crops grown in between trees) in these fields were under shallow tillage. Despite of high soil disturbance to high depths due to uprooting of old trees, the cultivation of crops in between trees and shallow tillage may explain why SOM contents were high in these fields. In these fields also, synthetic fertilizers were applied and ~50% of residues were returned in field after the harvest of crops. This incorporation of organic matter from crop residues and the application of synthetic fertilizer also explains high SOM than orchards. Other factors such as two species of ants that were common in all study fields may also be responsible for keeping these fields cultivable for centuries.

Conclusion

In this study, three orchards, three croplands and three tree-based intercropping (TBI) system fields were sampled. Orchards were ~250 years old with continuous uprooting of roots for replacement with saplings. This deep soil profile disturbance might be the cause of significantly lower SOM contents than croplands and TBI system fields, which were under shallow tillage practices. However, the application of

manure with synthetic fertilizers and the presence of two species of ants in orchards may explain why despite of deep soil profile disturbance for centuries, these fields were still cultivable. The croplands were 30 to 30 years old. Shallow tillage, ~50% residue return after the harvest of crops and the application of synthetic fertilizer (urea and nitrophos) may be the reason for significantly higher SOM contents than orchards. Although the TBI system fields were ~300 to 350 of age, these fields were under shallow tillage where the crops were grown, approximately 50% of residue return and the application of synthetic fertilizers might be the reasons of high SOM contents than orchards. Our results provide a clear evidence that deep soil disturbance has a negative effect on soil organic matter stocks of the agricultural lands of this region. This depletion of SOM has a negative influence on crops. Because Turbat is an agrarian region, the farmers of this region ought to adopt management practices that increase the SOM concentration. Shallow tillage, residue return and the co-application of manure and synthetic fertilizers in these fields are recommended to keep the SOM contents high and soil cultivable. Furthermore, tree-based intercropping systems need to be adopted as a major cropping system for SOM accrual and biodiversity of soil mesofauna and macrofauna.

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